

1 : 1

30 ml : 30 ml

Real Images of the used parts to build the device

Putting the device into the Housing

1

2

3

Used Parts to mount the device on a cow

1

2

3

Pulling the strap through the device

Real Image of an Open Source Animal Tracker

